

A Hospital Based Study to Assess Outcome of Tubeless Mini- Percutaneous Nephrolithotomy (PCNL) for the Treatment of Large (>20 Mm) Renal StonesNitesh Kumar¹, Shivanand Prakash², Karthik Maripeddi³, Sunil Palve⁴, Sanath T⁵¹Consultant Urologist, Ford Hospital and Research Centre, Patna, Bihar, India²Assistant Professor, Department of Urology, Narayan Medical College and Hospital, Sasaram, Bihar, India³Consultant Urologist, Vijay Merie Hospital, Hyderabad, India⁴Consultant Urologist, Medicover Hospital, Pune, Maharashtra, India⁵Mch Urology, Aadhya Hospital, Madanpally, Andhra Pradesh, India

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:**Aim:** The aim of this study was to evaluate the outcomes of tubeless mini- percutaneous nephrolithotomy (PCNL) for the treatment of large (>20 mm) renal stones.**Methods:** The study included consecutive adult patients who underwent mini-PCNL for large (>20 mm) renal stones for the period of 1 years. Preoperative, operative, postoperative, and follow-up data during outpatients' visits were prospectively recorded and maintained using a computer database. The data were retrospectively analyzed. The study included 100 patients in the study.**Results:** The study included 200 patients with mean age 42.8 ± 12.8 years (range 18–79) and mean stone size 30.5 ± 9.7 mm (range 20–70). Mean operative time was 62.8 ± 30.4 min (range 25–180). The average number of tracts per renal unit was 1.26. Mean hospital stay was 2.9 ± 0.9 days. The overall intraoperative and 30-day postoperative complication rate was 7%, with the majority being Clavien classification Grades I and II. Minor Grade (I–II) complications included postoperative fever requiring antibiotics in cases, postoperative haematuria requiring blood transfusion in two cases, severe postoperative pain requiring prolonged opioid analgesia in two cases, and perinephric hematoma that was managed conservatively in two cases. Grade III complications were observed in only 1% as one patient required renal angioembolization for severe hematuria 7 days following the procedure. On multivariate analysis, independent risk factor for significant residual stones was the presence of the stones in multiple sites inside the PCS (relative risk: 13.44, 95% confidence interval: 1.78–101.43, P = 0.012).**Conclusion:** Mini-PCNL is a safe and effective treatment for the management of adult patients with large renal stones. Stones located in multiple sites inside the PCS is the only predictor of unsuccessful outcome.**Keywords:** Mini-PCNL, RIRS, Stone.

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Introduction

Urinary stone disease has affected humankind for centuries, with worldwide rises in incidence and prevalence in recent decades. The lifetime prevalence of nephrolithiasis in Asia is 1–5%, with a 50% recurrence rate within 5 years. [1] Urologists employ minimally-invasive endoscopic surgeries to maximize stone clearance and minimize complications. Due to a higher stone clearance rate as compared with extracorporeal shockwave lithotripsy or retrograde intrarenal surgery, percutaneous nephrolithotomy (PCNL) is the first-line treatment for renal stones > 2 cm. [2] However, the better stone-free rate (SFR) of PCNL comes at the expense of greater risks and complications,

such as blood loss or a longer length of stay (LOS), owing to its invasiveness. [3] As compared with standard PCNL, mini-PCNL (defined by a percutaneous tract ranging from 11 to 20 French, F, in diameter) carries a lower risk of complications while achieving a similar SFR. Cheng et al [4] showed that mini-PCNL resulted in a better SFR for multiple calyceal or staghorn stones at the expense of a greater surgical duration, but resulted in fewer bleeding complications. However, the reported complications associated with mini-PCNL vary among studies. Bleeding complications requiring transfusion and/or arterial embolization in mini-PCNL studies were attributed to a larger stone

burden, which required multiple renal access tracts. [5]

Nephrolithiasis is a common worldwide disease with a rising incidence in the last few decades. [6] Current practice based on international guidelines, suggest percutaneous nephrolithotomy (PCNL) as the primary treatment for renal stones >20 mm, which is performed via 24–30F percutaneous renal dilatation. [2,4] Although this technique offers excellent stone-free rates, it has a relatively high incidence of complications with a systematic review by Seitz et al. in 2012 of 11,929 patients demonstrating an overall complication rate of 23.3%. [7] Recent evidence, including a systematic review, has identified that tract size is the main factor affecting blood loss during PCNL. [8,9]

In an attempt to reduce the morbidity, miniaturization of renal access size in PCNL was first introduced by Helal et al. in 1997. [10] Over the next two decades, several techniques of miniaturized PCNL (mini-Perc, mini-PCNL, or minimally invasive PCNL) have been described using 14–20F percutaneous renal dilatation with the primary goal to achieve high stone-free rates with the reduction in procedure-related complications. More recently, even smaller renal access systems have been described, including ultra-mini PCNL with 11–13F sheath, super-mini PCNL with 10–14F sheath, mini-micro PCNL with 8F sheath and micro-PCNL with <5F sheath. [11] Evidence for the superiority of any individual technique is poor with heterogeneous outcomes.

The aim of this study was to evaluate the outcomes of tubeless mini-percutaneous nephrolithotomy (PCNL) for the treatment of large (>20 mm) renal stones.

Materials and Methods

The study included consecutive adult patients who underwent mini-PCNL for large (>20 mm) renal stones for the period of 1 year at Ford Hospital and Research Centre, Patna, Bihar, India. Preoperative, operative, postoperative, and follow-up data during outpatients' visits were prospectively recorded and maintained using a computer database. The data were retrospectively analyzed. The study included 100 patients in the study.

Exclusion criteria were concomitant ipsilateral obstructing ureteric calculi. Stone size was defined as the largest dimension of a single stone or the sum of the largest dimensions of multiple stones. Variables included were age, sex, stone location, history of urolithiasis, Guy's stone score,¹² stone size, percutaneous tract location and numbers, perioperative hemoglobin change, hospital stay, stone-free status, and 30-day complications. Noncontrast computed tomography (NCCT) was the preoperative diagnostic modality for all

patients. All procedures adhered to the ethical guidelines of Declaration of Helsinki and its amendments. All patients included in the study provided a consent for undergoing the procedure. The authors confirm the availability of, and access to, all original data reported in this study.

Surgical Technique

All procedures were carried out under spinal anesthesia by a single surgeon (SK) at a tertiary care hospital. In the lithotomy position, a 6F ureteric catheter was secured at the level of the ipsilateral pelvi-ureteric junction. The patient was then turned to the prone position and secured on the operating table with padding of the chest and pelvis and pressure points. Prepping and draping were done, so the tip of the ureteric catheter was accessible in the sterile field. A fluoroscopic guided renal puncture was performed using 2 planes (0°C and 30°C-arm rotation) after retrograde pyelography to enable access to the desired calyx.

The preferred percutaneous entry point of the operating surgeon was a supra 12th rib approach with an interpolar renal puncture to allow accessibility to almost all the pelvic-calyceal system (PCS) through a single tract providing there was at least mild hydronephrosis. A 0.035-inch Zebra Guidewire (Boston Scientific, USA) was passed to the PCS and either secured down the ureter or coiled in a renal calyx. The needle was removed, and either a single-step or serial dilatation was performed using fascial dilators with the eventual placement of a 16, 18, or 20F peel-away renal access sheath.

The 12F mini-nephroscope (MIP, Karl Storz Endoskope, Tuttlingen, Germany) was connected to an intermittent flow irrigation system, which enabled high flow irrigation for <3 s followed by a subsequent 2 s pause. A pneumatic ballistic lithotripter with a 1.2F probe was used to disintegrate the stones. Fragment evacuation was achieved by a combination of the vacuum cleaner effect and saline flushing through the retrograde ureteral catheter. Tri-radiate grasper was rarely used to remove persistent stone fragments. At the end of the procedure, the ureteric catheter was removed, and an antegrade double-J stent was placed. No nephrostomy tubes were placed even in patients who required multiple tracts. Operative time was calculated from the insertion of the ureteric catheter till ureteric stent insertion.

Complications were recorded and classified according to the modified Clavien-Dindo classification.¹³ Stone-free status was evaluated with X-ray kidney-ureter-bladder for radiopaque stones and NCCT for radiolucent stones within 2 weeks after PCNL. Patients were declared stone-free if they had complete clearance or an

insignificant residual renal fragment <4 mm. Stent removal was performed under topical anesthesia 2–4 weeks after the procedure if no significant residual fragments were seen.

Statistical Analysis

The data were stored and analyzed using SPSS

(v20) software (IBM SPSS Statistics, Armonk, NY, USA). Univariate analysis (Chi-square or t-test)

was used to compare the variables between stone-free patients and those with significant residual fragments. Multivariate logistic regression analysis was used to define independent risk factors. $P < 0.05$ was considered to indicate statistical significance.

Results

Table 1: Operative data and postoperative outcomes of mini-percutaneous nephrolithotomy for large renal stones

Variables	n (%)
Number of percutaneous tracts	
One	81 (81)
Two	14 (14)
Three	4 (4)
Four	1 (1)
Location of percutaneous tracts	
Upper calyx	9 (9)
Mid calyx	54 (54)
Lower calyx	21 (21)
Multi-calyceal	16 (16)
Stone-free status	87 (87)
Complications	7 (7)
Grades I-II	8 (8)
Grade III	1 (1)
Blood transfusion	2 (2)

The study included 200 patients with mean age 42.8 ± 12.8 years (range 18–79) and mean stone size 30.5 ± 9.7 mm (range 20–70). Mean operative time was 62.8 ± 30.4 min (range 25–180). The average number of tracts per renal unit was 1.26. Mean hospital stay was 2.9 ± 0.9 days. The overall intraoperative and 30-day postoperative complication rate was 7%, with the majority being Clavien classification Grades I and II. Minor Grade (I–II) complications included postoperative fever

requiring antibiotics in cases, postoperative haematuria requiring blood transfusion in two cases, severe postoperative pain requiring prolonged opioid analgesia in two cases, and perinephric hematoma that was managed conservatively in two cases. Grade III complications were observed in only 1% as one patient required renal angioembolization for severe hematuria 7 days following the procedure.

Table 2: Univariate analysis of factors affecting stone-free status for mini-percutaneous nephrolithotomy of large renal stones

Categorical variables	Total (n=100)	Stone free (n=86; 86), n (%)	P
Gender			
Male	25	22	0.224
Female	75	64	
Previous stone treatment			
No	70	62	0.210
Yes	30	24	
Laterality			
Left	45	42	0.565
Right	55	44	
Stone size (mm)			
20-40 mm	85	74	0.055
>40 mm	15	12	
Stone location			
Renal pelvis	25	25	0.007
Single calyx	10	8	
Multiple sites	65	53	

Staghorn stones			
No	72	70	0.003
Yes	28	16	
Guy's stone score			
1	20	20	0.025
2	50	42	
3	15	11	
4	15	13	

On multivariate analysis, independent risk factor for significant residual stones was the presence of the stones in multiple sites inside the PCS (relative risk: 13.44, 95% confidence interval: 1.78–101.43, $P = 0.012$).

Discussion

The renal stone has upgrading role in the morbidity and quality of life of patients and its prevalence is about 10%. [14] Also, the recurrence of renal stones may be up to 50%. [15] The impact of recent technology on the kidney stone management has a great role, especially the advancement of minimally invasive technique such as extracorporeal shock wave lithotripsy (ESWL), percutaneous nephrolithotomy (PCNL), retrograde intra renal surgery (RIRS). [16]

The surgical technique of mini-PCNL in this study has been adapted from the Chinese method described by Li et al. of Guangzhou Medical College in China. [17] They reported a stone-free rate of 89% in their retrospective series, which contained 4760 mini-PCNLs. This is slightly more than the 86% stone-free rate in the present study, but they reported their experience with all stone sizes while we reported only for large stones.

The study included 200 patients with mean age 42.8 ± 12.8 years (range 18–79) and mean stone size 30.5 ± 9.7 mm (range 20–70). Mean operative time was 62.8 ± 30.4 min (range 25–180). The average number of tracts per renal unit was 1.26. Mean hospital stay was 2.9 ± 0.9 days.

The overall intraoperative and 30-day postoperative complication rate was 7%, with the majority being Clavien classification Grades I and II. Minor Grade (I–II) complications included postoperative fever requiring antibiotics in cases, postoperative haematuria requiring blood transfusion in two cases, severe postoperative pain requiring prolonged opioid analgesia in two cases, and perinephric hematoma that was managed conservatively in two cases. Grade III complications were observed in only 1% as one patient required renal angioembolization for severe hematuria 7 days following the procedure. Zeng et al. published the largest series of mini-PCNL outcomes of 13,984 cases. [18] This retrospective series analyzed 7234 complex stones. They reported an average of 1.25 tract per renal unit,

with 79.3% single tract procedures. In the present study, similar results were observed (1.26 average number of tracts with 80% performed through a single tract). Another advantage of mini-PCNL in the treatment of large renal stones is the ability to access most of the PCS through one tract, as shown in this study and Zeng et al. study. [18] The reason for the use of a single tract in 76% of cases in this study is attributed to the preference of accessing the PCS through the middle calyx. This interpolar renal access enabled accessibility to almost all the PCS and therefore allowing complete stone clearance without the need for multiple tracts in the majority of cases. [19] Recently, Lahme published outcomes of mini-PCNL for larger stones >5 cm² in 321 patients and reported a stone-free rate of 94.7%. [20] However, this was achieved after a retreatment rate of 38.7%.

The main advantage of mini-PCNL is lesser bleeding-related complications compared with standard PCNL. In a systematic review, complications of standard PCNL included blood transfusion in 7% of cases and an average hemoglobin drop of 2.3 g/dL. In the present study, these bleeding complications were decreased as blood transfusion was needed in 1.5%, and the average hemoglobin drop was 1.3 g/dL. Moreover, lower overall and Clavien-Dindo grade III-V complication rates were observed in this study compared with that of the standard PCNL from Seitz's review (Grade III: 8.4% vs. 23.3% and Grade IV: 0.9% vs. 4.74% respectively). [7] A randomized controlled trial by Cheng et al. in 2010 found that blood loss and the need for blood transfusion was significantly lower in mini-PCNL using a 16F sheath compared to standard 24F PCNL ($P < 0.05$). [21]

On multivariate analysis, independent risk factor for significant residual stones was the presence of the stones in multiple sites inside the PCS (relative risk: 13.44, 95% confidence interval: 1.78–101.43, $P = 0.012$). Another advantage of mini-PCNL is omitting the need for nephrostomy tube placement after the procedure in most cases. A meta-analysis comparing tubeless versus standard PCNL procedures reported that tubeless procedures led to shorter hospital stay, less postoperative pain, and possibly quicker recovery. [23] The mean hospital stay in this study was 2.9 days because all patients were admitted 1 day prior to surgery and stayed for

one or 2 days after the procedure as per hospital policy. When looking for risk factors for residual stones in this study, the presence of stones in multiple sites inside the PCS was the only independent predictor in multivariate analysis. Of note, neither Guy's classification for stone burden nor the presence of staghorn stones was a significant risk factor in predicting residual stones in multivariate analysis. The stone size was not significant in univariate analysis. This indicated the versatility of mini-PCNL for the treatment of various stone burdens.

Conclusion

Mini-PCNL is a safe and effective treatment for the management of adult patients with large renal stones. Stones located in multiple sites inside the PCS is the only predictor of unsuccessful outcome.

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